

VET4YOUTH TEAM

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Stemming the tide Tackling **early leaving** from VET in times of **crises** Synthesis report of Cedefop/ReferNet survey

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Research paper

Stemming the tide: tackling early leaving from vocational education and training in times of crises

Synthesis report of Cedefop/ReferNet survey

DOI: 10.2801/757603

Focus of key research questions

- ✓ **National definitions** and **collection of specific data** on early leaving from VET (ELVET) to inform policy making
- ✓ National / regional / institutional **initiatives and mechanisms to detect and support** in a timely manner learners at risk of dropping out and early leavers
- ✓ Main **factors leading to ELVET**
- ✓ Monitoring of **possible effects of Covid-19 on the learning process** in initial VET
- ✓ **Support offered to Ukrainian refugees** for their integration into national VET systems

Source: Synthesis report of Cedefop/ReferNet survey, 2023

Questionnaire and responses

- ✓ Questionnaire sections structured in line with research questions
- ✓ 28 responses were received, covering **26 EU Member States** (Malta not included), **Norway and Iceland**
- ✓ Limited information on Ireland and Croatia
- ✓ Belgium provided information on its three regions separately; as a result, the three regions of Belgium are treated as separate units in the figures
- ✓ Overall analysis and figures are, therefore, based on **30 responses**

Source: Synthesis report of Cedefop/ReferNet survey, 2023

Cedefop's working definition of ELVET

ELVET

- (a) referring to persons aged 18 to 24;
- (b) the highest level of education or training they have completed is ISCED 2011 level 0, 1 or 2 (ISCED 1997: 0, 1, 2 or 3C short);
- (c) have started vocational training at ISCED level 3 or 4 but did not receive an upper secondary VET qualification;
- (d) they have not received any education or training (i.e. neither formal nor non-formal) in the 4 weeks preceding the survey (currently not engaged in education and training).

- ✓ Only **Latvia** and **Hungary** explicitly reported that a definition of ELVET is available, although not fully addressing Cedefop's criteria
- ✓ **Other indicators or definitions** used and monitored instead of ELVET (EU definition of ELET and different dropout measurements)

Source: Synthesis report of Cedefop/ReferNet survey, 2023

Data characteristics in case of regular data collection

Monitoring early leavers

Centralised system gathering nominal information on early leavers

- ✓ Exists in BE-DE, BE-FL and 14 more countries
- ✓ Does not exist in BE-FR and 12 more countries
- ✓ No information available in 1 country (HR)

Local or coordinated services responsible for getting in touch with early leavers and referring them to relevant measures

- ✓ At national and regional level in BE-FL and 12 more countries
- ✓ At national level only in 1 country (LV)
- ✓ At regional level only in BE-DE, BE-FR and 4 more countries

Availability of services for identifying learners at risk

Most frequent factors leading to dropout

1. Low overall education achievement and attendance

- ✓ Always or often in 7 countries (BE-DE, CZ, DK, EE, IT, LT and AT), sometimes in 8 countries (BE-FL, FI, DE, IS, LV, NL, PT and RO)

2. Health and well-being issues

- ✓ Always or often in BE-DE, sometimes in 11 countries (BE-FR, AT, DE, DK, EE, FI, IS, IT, LT, LV, NL)

3. Lack of family engagement and support

- ✓ Always or often in 3 countries (CZ, IT, AT), sometimes in 8 countries (DK, FI, DE, IS, LV, LT, NL, RO)

4. Lack of or insufficient guidance to support VET learners' choices

- ✓ Sometimes in 10 countries (AT, BE-DE, CZ, EE, FI, DE, IS, IT, LT, NL)

Least frequent factors leading to dropout

1. Systemic/structural reasons (e.g. low permeability of the education system; early differentiation and track selection)

- ✓ Rarely or never in 7 countries (BE-DE, DK, FI, IS, LV, LT and PT), sometimes in 4 countries (BE-FL, CZ, DE and AT)

2. Lack of apprenticeship placements or other in-company training

- ✓ Rarely or never in 6 countries (BE-DE, CZ, DE, LT, NO and PT), sometimes in 5 countries (AT, FI, IS, IT and NL)

3. Poor employment outcomes for VET graduates, i.e. due to unattractiveness of the labour market (e.g. VET qualifications lead to low-paid jobs)

- ✓ Rarely or never in 5 countries (BE-DE, BE-FR, DK, IT, LV, AT), sometimes in 5 countries (FI, DE, IS, LT, RO)

4. Unsatisfactory working conditions during their work-based learning

- ✓ Rarely or never in 5 countries (BE-DE, IS, LV, LT, RO), sometimes in 5 countries (BE-FR, DK, IT, AT, FI)

5. Inappropriate/unattractive teaching methods

- ✓ Rarely or never in 3 countries (BE-FR, BE-DE, LV, LT), sometimes in 6 countries (DK, EE, DE, NL, AT, FI)

Monitoring the participation of VET learners in online distance learning in school-based and work-based settings

Support to learners in school-based learning during school closures

Support to learners in work-based learning during company closures

Support to VET schools and companies, teachers and trainers

- ✓ In school-based learning settings:
 - most countries provided teachers with access to free equipment and internet connection as well as with training to use digital tools and platforms
 - only half of the countries provided access to psychological and mental health support
- ✓ Financial support to train teachers and trainers on digital skills and tools: became available in 12 countries for schools and in 3 countries for companies providing work-based learning
- ✓ In work-based learning settings:
 - in most countries, no support measures were taken or no relevant information became available

Support to Ukrainian refugee students

Key policy messages

Building comparable data on ELVET

- Further research is needed to investigate possible avenues for improving the existing national and European data on ELVET on a regular basis

Complementing quantitative data with qualitative data

- Coexistence of various reasons for dropping out to be considered
- Important reasons, such as the academic underachievement, to be included
- Reasons specific to school or work-based learning within a VET programme to be identified

Focusing on drop out in work-based learning

- Equal priority should be given to lowering the rates of early leaving in companies to comprehensively tackle the phenomenon of early leaving from VET

Offering quality CPD on inclusion

- Provision of quality CPD to promote inclusion for VET teachers and trainers should be sustainable and consolidated
- Focus on digital inclusion to support vulnerable VET learners by enhancing their access to and use of digital means

European Survey of VET teachers (EVTS)

Sept 2025 - June 2026

To address existing research gaps:

- Understand VET teachers' continuing professional (CPD) needs (e.g. digital & green skills, inclusion)
- Measure different CPD activities and variation across VET teachers
- Get insight into drivers of VET teachers' CPD
- Measure CPD effectiveness (skills, job performance)

VET toolkit for tackling early leaving

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

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Thank you

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